

Ethics perspective and regulation of plagiarism in Higher Education

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Abstract

Plagiarism is no longer a mere issue, but it is a global fact that this disease has attacked higher education, and regarding ethics, immoral and irresponsible academics has shaken the world of education. Plagiarism has become a systematic virus that must be tackled from the root of the problem. Plagiarism is the responsibility of higher education with the government in which the Indonesian government of higher education has already established its legislation on plagiarism and colleges elaborate on it in their respective academic rules. The prevention of plagiarism begins with building a winning, honest, anti-plagiarism, and responsible mentality. It also provides a plagiarism prevention system manual (manual regulation and regulation through editorial team, plagiarism law socialization, honest and responsible culture building), as well as the use of anti-plagiarism software in college and internet and mobile browsing. Plagiarism at a high altitude can kill the creativity and wealth of thinking of pouring new ideas into work. Students who do plagiarism means to have shut down their intellectual honesty in their work. While systems that allow plagiarism to occur that they have shut down the integrity of students in work and destroy the creativity of other students in college who uphold honesty in the work.

Keywords:

Plagiarism; ethics; regulation; education; laws; prevention; systems; editors

1 INTRODUCTION

Plagiarism in Indonesia's higher education has a high potential of occurring. Even for colleges whose scientific works have not yet been published online, the potential for plagiarism is very high. Higher education institutes that do not apply rules or legislation have a higher potential for the occurrence of plagiarism. This error occurs because there is no system or rules that regulate plagiarism in these institutes or there is an attitude of omission of plagiarism.

Higher education wants the quality of education in Indonesia to be improved, but on the other hand, prevention and control of plagiarism are not optimal. The quality of education is measured through scientific works produced by students where there is no potential for plagiarism. Educational institutions are responsible for this, and students are only obedient to the rules

set. This article explained about definitions of plagiarism, causes of plagiarism, legal sanctions for plagiarists, ethics, regulation and solution to avoid plagiarism in high education.

Plagiarism is a deliberate or intentional act of obtaining or attempting to obtain credit or value for a scientific work, quoting part or all of the work and/or scientific work of another party acknowledged as a scientific work, without declaring the source appropriately and adequately. Although the definitions for plagiarism or duplicate publication may vary and “gray zones” for definitions may exist, intentional copy-editing from other papers is strongly discouraged. Often, paraphrasing another author’s idea but using one’s statements together with citing the original article can help avoid the criticism of plagiarism (Lee, 2008). Plagiarism is a worldwide problem, which arises in various diverse zones of our lives. There are many different forms of plagiarism.

Plagiarism happens when one claims that an idea, or the expression of it, is his own when in fact it is someone else’s. Plagiarism is defined as “The practice of taking someone else’s work or ideas and passing them off as one’s own.” It is also defined as “The use of another author’s language, thoughts, ideas, or expressions, and or the representation of them as one’s original work without crediting the source” (Mohammed et al., 2015). Plagiarism is a deliberate or intentional act of obtaining or attempting to obtain credit or value for a scientific work, quoting part or all of the work and/or scientific work of another party acknowledged as a scientific work, without declaring the source appropriately and adequately.

Many of the plagiarism policies echo these elements as plagiarism is often defined as an act of dishonesty (sometimes also called misconduct) in which an object (property) in the form of words, ideas, artwork, computer programs, and the like are misappropriated (taken, stolen) by a person (offender) from another person or source (Sutherland-Smith, 2011). Based on the description of plagiarism above, it can be concluded that plagiarism is quoting or taking part of the writing, either the ideas, words, quotations in quotations, and translations without listing the true source, including the source quoted by the previous author. When authors intentionally or unintentionally falsify the author's identity, title, and publisher, year and page, which is also plagiarism.

The view that it is not easy to detect plagiarism. However, from existing research, this view is more appropriate. According to the nature of the plagiarized production, plagiarism can occur in many types, including plagiarism of ideas, text, designs, collusion, self-plagiarism, patchwriting and many others (Mohammed et al., 2015). Plagiarism of ideas is very difficult to detect because of a lack of proof and because there is no real production stolen (Mohammed et al., 2015). It is the theft of a new idea or a theory presented anywhere. The plagiarist then conducts research based on this idea/theory and presents it as if it is his/her own without acknowledgment of the source (Mohammed et al., 2015). This section is tough to detect if the idea has been translated in the language of the researcher himself and eliminated the source. Therefore a researcher must protect his or her idea with copyright.

The incorporation of borrowed words and ideas into written work, however, is a delicate and complicated issue. If a writer fails to give credit in an appropriate way to the source of the borrowed material in her text, the stigmatizing label of “plagiarism” may be applied. In a university context, if students include what are perceived as plagiarized ideas or words in their writing, they may encounter serious problems that can threaten their academic future (Kobayashi & Rinnert, 2005). Plagiarism of text. This form is also known as “copy-cut-paste” or “word-to-word” writing. This occurs when a searcher takes an entire paragraph from another source and includes it in his research writing (Mohammed et al., 2015).

Self-plagiarism occurs when a researcher uses substantial parts of his research in two different publications that use the same findings or illustrations without referring to both publications. This form of plagiarism is also known as “redundant data.” There is a debate about self-plagiarism to consider if it is misconduct at all (Mohammed et al., 2015). Also known as text recycling, is another common form of plagiarism. In self-plagiarism, the author copies large parts of one of his or her previous papers word-for-word (Emmanuel, Carver, Dellva, & Parchure, 2011). Authors often forget to provide a source or footnote for their writings cited in other writings. This also happens when the writing is published online in many places, but it is almost the same, so it can be called self-plagiarism.

Collusion is allowing someone else, such as professionals or agencies, with or without paying money, to write a piece of work and then the plagiarist presents it as if it is his/her own. This is a form of illegal, unauthorized cooperation with the intent to deceive (Mohammed et al., 2015). Plagiarists hire services who do not know the rules of plagiarism to creating scientific writings with sources that are not clear and which they indeed lead to plagiarism and lawlessness. Patchwriting is copying parts of another work and changing a few words or the order of words to make it appear as if it is original. This should not be mixed with paraphrasing, which is taking a fact from a source then writing it in one’s language and style. Paraphrasing is appropriate, while patchwriting is not (Mohammed et al., 2015; Li, 2013). The writer takes part of the quote and replaces the words with his own words so that it looks like his writing, but he/she does not provide the source of the writing or ideas, so it is also plagiarism. The author can narrate a quote but must include the source so as not to plagiarize.

There are many causes of plagiarism as follows: (Mohammed et al., 2015)

- a) Misunderstanding: many researchers believe that taking entire paragraphs from different papers and including them in their writing is accepted as long as they mention the references at the end. The result will be a new article having substantial parts in the “copy-cut-paste” style, which is the definition of plagiarism. Submitted articles in this style are rejected by journals or may be retracted after being published.
- b) Poor time management and writing under stress. The author does not focus on his research because he/she takes care of many other jobs that take much time.
- c) Immature writing skills: scientific writing is a language that undergoes development over time. The essential tool to gain this skill is an excessive

reading of literature and practice of scientific writing. Over time, writing research articles becomes an enjoyable experience.

- d) Intentional, as previously discussed. This part must have been the researcher's intention from the beginning.
- e) One of the most common causes of plagiarism is the enormous pressure on researchers and academic staff to publish their studies: the 'publish or perish' rule. The pressure of academic promotion and reporting of research results is too enormous. Therefore, researchers should not work alone but as a team of researchers to share tasks and responsibilities in research.

Pecorari and Petrić say other causes of plagiarism:

Plagiarism has long been used as an umbrella term covering various types of unacceptable behavior, some of which, but not all, refer to textual activity. Poor referencing, poor paraphrase and inaccurate citation are sometimes placed in the same category as commissioning a paper from commercial service and submitting another student's paper as one's own (Pecorari & Petrić, 2014).

2 METHOD

This study aims to provide the description and comprehension of the ethics and regulation of plagiarism in higher education. This paper used a method of the literature review. Literature reviews should "objectively report the current knowledge on an issue" and afford a summary of the best current study from earlier available studies related to a specific topic (Baker, 2016; Green, Johnson, & Adams, 2006). Information used to write this paper was collected from the sources of journal and books.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Legal Sanctions for Plagiarists

Universities' plagiarism policies vary significantly in the extent of detail given about the act of plagiarism. Some universities are very detailed, and break down plagiarism into categories such as "serious," "moderate," and "slight" plagiarism and give percentages of permitted copied text to determine the level of plagiarism in each category. Different penalties are then attached to different levels of the offense depending on the seriousness of the plagiarism (Sutherland-Smith, 2011).

The notion that plagiarism is an illegal conceivably even a criminal act, intended to harm another author is aligned with the way in which copyright legislation penalizes breaches of the copyright law (Sutherland-Smith, 2005). The Education Law in Indonesia regulates specifically about plagiarism as a form of protection of scientific work of researchers. The sanctions are as follows: First, College graduates who use scientific works to obtain an academic degree, profession, or vocation, if plagiarism is proved, his title will be repealed. Second, Graduates whose scholarly work he uses to earn an academic degree, profession, or vocation as referred to in Article 25 Paragraph 2 and it is proven to be a copy will be convicted with a maximum imprisonment of two years and/or a fine of at most hundred million rupiahs.

Ministerial Regulation has set sanctions for students who plagiarized. If plagiarism is proven, then students will receive the following sanctions:

- a) Warning
- b) Written warning
- c) Delay granting part of the student's rights
- d) Cancellation of value
- e) Dismissal concerning status as a student
- f) Dismissal not concerning status as a student
- g) Cancellation of a diploma if the individual has graduated from the education process.

3.2 Some Results of Research on Plagiarism

In recent years, research has become a growing industry. There is fierce competition among more than 7.1 million researchers in the world to have their research published in over 25,000 journals. Researchers are under pressure to get their work published in good journals. When this pressure is coupled with a lack of time, lack of research skills and ease of obtaining information and articles from the internet, the rate of plagiarism increases (Mohammed et al., 2015).

According to the results of other studies in a sample of 62,213 MEDLINE citations, 0.04% of cases were examples of potential plagiarism and 1.35% of cases were considered duplicate publications. After extrapolation, this corresponded to as many as 3,500 and 117,500 cases of total citations, respectively (Lee, 2008). In another report, Zhang used the text analysis service CrossCheck to detect articles submitted to the Journal of Zhejiang University – Science (JZUS). The results of the study also designate the restricted use of the notion of “culture”, which is often cited in explaining plagiarism among EAL authors. The Chinese editor referred to previously, for example, reported a “staggering 31%” of the submissions to the JZUS contained plagiarism (Li, 2012).

Results from studies conducted in Australia (32% of 186 students in (Sutherland-Smith, 2010) and the UK (32.2% of 291 students, (Szabo & Underwood, 2004)) are almost identical to the figures from US studies reviewed above. The only exception is Selwyn who reveals much higher figures. However, this may be due to the diversity in the phrasing of the feedback options in the survey since Selwyn used a definite time frame rather than the frequency scales used in other studies. The study may account for the apparent difference in students’ responses (Pecorari & Petrić, 2014; Selwyn, 2008). The results of the study is expected to help higher education to improve the socialization of the dangers of plagiarism concerning the research ethics code in universities. The above proves that on the one hand students want to give their best work, but the potential for plagiarism is also high. Higher education can reduce the level of plagiarism with two things that are done at the level of law (ethics, norms, and regulation) and the level of skill by using anti-plagiarism software tools.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Ethics And Plagiarism

Yolanda Lira shared in *Higher Education – Ethics in Action Global Ethics Forum 2016 The Value of Values across Sectors*. She said:

Raising awareness for academic honesty, integrity and building a culture of ethical research can successfully be done among faculty and students by discussing case studies and best practices in curricular teachings. In practice, it is important to offer incentives aiming at awarding authentic research, or by the promotion of “demonstrated moral integrity (Ethics, 2016).

Plagiarism is undoubtedly a disgraceful and selfish act and includes the act of “stealing” which harms others. Usually, plagiarism occurs because people who do research are people who are not smart, not creative, lazy to learn and want to find the easy way to do things in conducting research. The act of cheating and theft is a sin. Every act of sin must be acknowledged and sanctioned by the rules. Applicable, in this case, is the sanction of student and academic regulations and if the perpetrator is a lecturer, he/she will be subject to sanctions by the lecturer's ethical code.

Integrity in academic life is essential to demonstrate responsible attitudes and principles in scientific work. Proper understanding and correct action will prevent a researcher from plagiarism. Anti-plagiarism and upholding ethical values, norms and rules in higher education will reflect the principle of National Education and pass on religious values. Honesty, integrity, and originality are the most critical aspects that should be considered carefully when someone creates a work, whereas a plagiarism act occurs when someone fails to provide sufficient source citation in one’s work. The values of ethics to avoid plagiarism, are scientific truth, reasoning, honesty, justice, benefits, virtue, responsibility, diversity, and affordability.

Heather Hilliard et al., said:

*An examination of the universities where a code of conduct existed found that the most common practice was defining the word “plagiarism.” Four out of five regions defined plagiarism with an emphasis on honesty **and integrity**. However, only two out of five regions provided guidelines for citation. While it is apparent that plagiarism is indeed a breach of university policy for all locations included in this research, only some of the universities outlined criminal actions associated with the subject (Hilliard, Crudele, Matulich, & McMurrian, 2011).*

4.2 The Solution to Avoid Plagiarism

One of the essential principles of holistic approach concerning plagiarism prevention was the creation of intolerant culture to plagiarism (Carroll & Appleton, 2001):

- a) The culture of involving and engaging students should be created: lecturers should have to provide exciting tasks and be open to students’ opinions and ideas and to explain the tasks. The number of deceptions should be less if students respect their lecturers are interested in their studies;

- b) Academic culture in an institution must be an example of good experience to students. Lecturers have to apply the same requirements to the students and themselves;
- c) Safe presentation, return, and system of evaluation of written works have to be used so, that students could not take the work of other student, works could not be lost, every student could get remarks from the lecturer and could be informed about advantages and disadvantages of his or her work.

Bretag summarizes this point and gives solutions to avoid plagiarism (Bretag, 2013):

- a) Plagiarism undermines the integrity of education and occurs at all levels of scholarship.
- b) Research indicates that both undergraduate and postgraduate students require training to avoid plagiarism.
- c) Established researchers are not immune to allegations of plagiarism.
- d) Educational institutions need to move beyond deterrence, detection, and punishment and take a holistic and multi-stakeholder approach to address plagiarism.

The understanding of plagiarism in Indonesian higher education for some universities has been implemented by publishing it online. Some universities also use plagiarism software. Also, some rules stipulate that a student must write a plagiarism-free statement. If plagiarism is found, it will be dealt with by the applicable rules. Lecturers or teachers should always give a statement in the classroom or during the guidance of the thesis or dissertation that plagiarism is unethical, not honorable and violates the law (Patak, Naim, & Talib, 2014; Patak, Naim, Talib, Akib, & Ghafar, 2015)

Higher education gives good examples and solutions to the students not to get trapped into plagiarism. Also, there is a college action through a higher education policy based on the education minister's decision on plagiarism that is passed on to the students. The action is realized in the code of academic ethics which leads to the information on the certificate of the accompanying diploma. Other solutions are formed by the editorial team in charge of evaluating the source text and at the same time setting the writing quality. If any writer finds plagiarism, then the solution is to remove the writing and replace it with the complete writing of the source. This is done before the author goes into the final exam as a graduation requirement in college. Early prevention of plagiarism benefits students and educational institutions where students study and complete their studies. The quality of education is also maintained and graduate students are also proud to be graduates of such institutions.

We should eliminate the opportunities for cheating and plagiarism, discourage, and in some cases, punish forms of cheating that represent high reputational risks. Convincing students that to study is the most convenient way of passing can be done by underlining the importance of ethics of esteem of others and reputation. Mechanisms of symbolic and economic rewards should be put in place to reinforce academic honesty and integrity (Ethics, 2016). Today's major publication ethical challenge mainly results from global

inequity. Open access to publications could be a solution, although it faces significant challenges as copyright constraints and dubious publishers. Management of the ethical issues in publication could be improved through the development and enforcement of policies from both individuals and institutions, applying the codes of publication ethics like copyright laws and ethical review (Ethics, 2016). Zhang said, “We campaign for authors, researchers and editors to be on the alert for plagiarism and to work against cultural misunderstandings” (Li, 2013; Zhang, 2010a).

This relative lack of students who deliberately set out to cheat is consistent with other studies (Macdonald & Carroll, 2006), and underlines the fact that education together with effective detection is a viable way to cut plagiarism. Today is the time to understand, prevent and act against plagiarism because if it does not start now, the next generation will be ruined by the culture of plagiarism today. Create a culture of honesty and integrity and mental revolution with the motto of let’s go, let’s be ethical and let’s not plagiarize (Say No To Plagiarism or Anti-Plagiarism).

5 CONCLUSION

Storms of plagiarism temporarily hit education in Indonesia, and plagiarism culture is widespread with the advancement of information and the ease of gaining access to scientific papers. If higher education does not improve, then the integrity of colleges will be hit by problems. Therefore, universities in Indonesia must rise up by building ethics and norms and rules to prevent and overcome plagiarism and plagiarism players in Indonesia. The prevention of plagiarism begins with building a winning, honest, honorable, anti-plagiarism, and responsible mentality. It also provides a plagiarism prevention system manual (a manual regulation and regulation through editorial team, plagiarism law socialization, honest and responsible culture building), as well as the use of anti-plagiarism software in colleges and internet and mobile browsing. Lecturers or teachers should provide excellent and honest attitudes in declaring plagiarism embodied in anti-plagiarism action so that students have anti-plagiarism attitudes and produce plagiarism-free scientific papers so that the institutions and students attain appreciation and pride from their best work.

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